

Job Satisfaction at Omega Technical Services Ltd

CHEK KEA^{1*}¹School of Management, Shanghai University, China

Accepted July 19,2021
Published July 22,2021

*Corresponding Author:
CHEK, KEA

DOI :<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5122823>

Pages: 59-66

Funding: CSC and Secretariat
General of the senate of the
Kingdom of Cambodia

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How to cite this article (APA):
CHEK KEA. (2021) Job
Satisfaction at Omega Technical
Services Ltd. *North American
Academic Research*, 4(7), 59-66
doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5122823>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the study of employees' job satisfaction at Omega Technical Services Ltd as a main factor of the firm, especially in the services sector, is becoming increasingly dependent upon high quality performance from their employees; as a trend reflected in the growing interest in the attitude of employees towards work. There are two factors have been argued to be influential. First, there exists a popular view that making work more satisfying will lead to increased motivation and performance, and to reduced absenteeism and labor turnover amongst employees. Second, it possible to identify a desire to provide satisfying work for ethical and altruistic reasons, regardless of the tangible benefits for the organization. According to these reasons the attention of managers has been drawn to strategies which attempt to increase employee satisfaction at work. To design a quality plan for improved job satisfaction, motivation that is the important point to identify staff attitude on job implementation. In generally used the method to establish the actions that company needs to take idea investigate or survey of the Job implementation.

Keywords: ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR, ADMINISTRATIVE STAFF, JOB SATISFACTION, MOTIVATION.

1. Introduction

Omega Technical Services Ltd is a medium sized company established in the mid-1950s to provide a range of technical support services to the

engineering industry. The majority of the company's work consists of providing a documentation service producing operational and maintenance manuals for clients involved with the design and installation of engineering projects in government departments and private sector originations. The commercial basis of the company's work is a mixture of fixed price contracts, won through competitive tenders and a smaller number of projects run on a 'cost plus' basis. In the latter the company is paid an hourly rate for the work done but the number of hours is not specified, in advance, by the client.

In 1984 the company experienced trading difficulties as a result of increased competition in the market place and in response to falling profits a period of rationalization began under the direction of a new financial director. This included a major redundancy programs and the relocation of the head office. Over a period of a

few months there were many changes in the management of the company particularly at line manager level and in the directors of the company.

The company is currently facing external pressures as a result of the recessionary climate and some significant changes in the market within which it operates. Clients undertaking military projects have been faced with the implications of the end of the cold war and the move by others away from cost plus contracts towards fixed priced tendering has led to a degree of uncertainty for the company (Anon n.d.).

This study is to propose, describe, and illustrate an approach to action research of Job satisfaction at Omega Technical Services Ltd. To make the best use of people as a valuable resource of the organization, attention must be given to the relationship between staff, and the nature and content of their jobs. The work organization and the design of jobs can have a significant effect on staff and their levels of performance and productivity. Attention needs to be given to the quality of working life. job satisfaction is important, not only because of a humanistic desire to improve the quality of work life, but also its potential impact on outcomes such as productivity and turnover (Smerek and Peterson 2007). The manager needs to understand how best to make work more satisfying for staff and to overcome obstacles to effective performance, How to develop an effective plan for improved job satisfaction? What approaches that personnel manager have use to appraisal employee attitudes and what advantage would these provide?

II. Discussion

A. Company organization and staffing

In order to achieve its goals and objectives the work of an organization has to be divided among its members. organizational structure The way in which job tasks are formally divided, grouped, and coordinated (Wenden 1981). Some structure is necessary to make possible the effective performance of key activities and to support the efforts of staff. Structure provides the framework of an organization and its pattern of management. It is by means of structure that the purpose and work of the organization is carried out. The manager needs to understand the importance and effects of organization structure (Mullins n.d.). Managers need to address six key elements when they design their organization's structure: work specialization, departmentalization, chain of command, span of control, centralization and decentralization, and formalization (Wenden 1981). According to Omega Technical Services Ltd is structured geographically with eight regional offices located close to its main clients in the South East (SE), South West (SW), North West (NW), and North East (NE) of England, the East Midlands (EM) and West Midlands (WM), the Home Counties (HC) and Scotland. A small head office of 12 staff, together with the six company directors and the personnel manager, is based at the South West regional office. The work in the regions is the responsibility of a regional manager who is encouraged to operate autonomously within his own market. Their work is supervised by one of two project leaders and typically only two administrative support staff is employed in each of these smaller offices. In total the company employs 180 full time staff, excluding the directors and personnel manager. The average age of all employees is 44 years and 38 per cent of the workforce is female.

The company has a formal recognition agreement with the Manufacturing, Science and Finance Union (MSF) and membership is in the order of 50 per cent of the workforce. Annual negotiations are held in September of each year to agree substantive matters including pay, allowances, holidays and hours of work. Regarding to The manufacturing foremen constituted the largest group of salaried employees at Lima. Foremen were employed primarily in four main areas: Production, Maintenance, Material Control, and Quality Assurance. One of the factors influencing the performance of line foremen on the job was their educational background and skill set. Treadway's management was debating whether to change the composition of the foreman candidate pool. As of December 2006, when Wall joined the Lima plant, its foremen came from three sources : the majority (80 %) were internal promotions of Lina 's unionized workers , a second group (16 %) were young graduates from the local colleges , and a select few (4 %) were experienced foremen transfers from other Treadway plants .Most successful general supervisors and area managers ranks(Anon n.d.).

Allocation of projects to individual employees is made by the regional manager in consultation with the project leaders. Liaison with clients on a day to day basis is the responsibility of the allocated employee and this may involve visits to the client's premises. The nature of the work requires employees with specialist knowledge of engineering work and well developed writing skills. Staff is recruited from employment backgrounds where such knowledge and skills have been developed. The definition of work requirements should look beyond individual responsibilities and incorporate the organization's mission, values, and strategy without sacrificing sound measurement(Anderson et al. n.d.).

❖ **Organizational Designs and Employee Behavior**

Organization's structure can have significant effects on its members. What might those effects be? We find fairly strong evidence linking centralization and job satisfaction. In general, less centralized organizations have a greater amount of autonomy. And autonomy appears positively related to job satisfaction. But, again, while one employee may value freedom, another may find autonomous environments frustratingly ambiguous. Our conclusion: to maximize employee performance and satisfaction, managers must take individual differences, such as experience, personality, and the work task, into account. Culture should factor in, too(Wenden 1981).

❖ **Conflict and negotiation**

The conflict is a process that begins when one party perceives that another party has negatively affected, or is about to negatively affects, something that the first party cares about that divided two parts:

- The Traditional View of Conflict

The early approach to conflict assumed all conflict was bad and to be avoided. Conflict was viewed negatively and discussed with such terms as violence, destruction, and irrationality to reinforce its negative connotation. The belief that all conflict is harmful and must be avoided.

- Interactionist view of conflict

The belief that conflict is not only a positive force in a group but also an absolute necessity for a group to perform effectively.

- Resolution-Focused View of Conflict

In sum, the traditional view was shortsighted in assuming all conflict should be eliminated. The interactionist view that conflict can stimulate active discussion without spilling over into negative, disruptive emotions is incomplete. The managed conflict perspective does recognize that conflict is probably inevitable in most organizations, and it focuses more on productive conflict resolution. The research pendulum has swung from eliminating conflict, to encouraging limited levels of conflict, and now to finding constructive methods for resolving conflicts productively so their disruptive influence can be minimized(Wenden 1981).

❖ Job Satisfaction

When people speak about employee attitudes, they usually mean job satisfaction, which describes a positive feeling about a job, resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics. What is job satisfaction? Job satisfaction is more of an attitude, an internal state. It could, for example, be associated with a personal feeling of achievement, either quantitative or qualitative(Mullins n.d.). The definition of job satisfaction is a positive feeling about a job resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics is clearly broad. A job is more than just shuffling papers, writing programming code, waiting on customers, or driving a truck. Jobs require interacting with co-workers and bosses, following organizational rules and policies, meeting performance standards, living with less than ideal working conditions, and the like. An employee's assessment of his satisfaction with the job is thus a complex summation of many discrete elements(Anderson et al. n.d.). The groups showed different demographic profiles and levels of job satisfaction, but their patterns of job satisfaction were similar(Hom 2018). job satisfaction appears relevant across cultures, that doesn't mean there are no cultural differences in job satisfaction(Wenden 1981).

❖ Dimensions of Job Satisfaction

There is some doubt whether job satisfaction consists of a single dimension or a number of separate dimensions(Mullins n.d.). Some workers may be satisfied with certain aspects of their work and dissatisfied with other aspects. However, it seems that there is no one, general, comprehensive theory which explains job satisfaction. The level of job satisfaction is affected by a wide range of variables relating to individual, social, cultural, organizational and environmental factors. Individual factors include personality, education and qualifications, intelligence and abilities, age, marital status, orientation to work. Social factors include relationships with co-workers, group working and norms, Opportunities for interaction, informal organization. Cultural factors include underlying attitudes, beliefs and values. Organizational factors include nature and size, formal structure, personnel policies and procedures, employee relations, nature of the work, technology and work organization, supervision and styles of leadership, management systems, working conditions. Environmental factors include economic, social, technical and governmental influences.

B. The Situation

Omega is a highly standardized organization seeking consistency in all its practices we have evidence of variations in the implementation of human resource practices and of employee views of the ways managers

exercise their discretion which led to increasing labour turnover and absenteeism. The company's drive towards improved quality and the external pressures it faces in the market place the board of directors is becoming increasingly concerned over what it perceives as a problem of low morale amongst employees and its possible impact upon performance. Middle managers have reported increased incidents of poor quality work and low productivity. Bellingham, the Lima plant manager, attributed the morale problem of the foremen primarily to lack of communication. Bellingham commented, "Foremen feel isolated from the rest of the plant. They are the lowest players on the totem pole, and they feel that their contributions are undervalued and their concerns ignored. Open communication is essential to this. As a perk, I have recently tried to introduce occasional social events after work for foremen, other salaried employees, and their managers a sports theme night at the local bar, for example. The foremen appreciate the gesture, but our general supervisors and area managers are not accustomed to this style of management or level of social interaction."(Anon n.d.)

❖ **Questionnaire design (Strengths and Weakness)**

The Personnel manager considered the options available to him and chose a survey technique of a tailor made, self-administered Questionnaire which he felt would ease analysis, be economical and produce results in a relatively short timescale. That comprised 83 items of which 68 were closed statements, 12 were open ended questions and three were of a demographic nature. The closed questions 67 sought to explore issues in five areas comprising: (i) general satisfaction, (ii) communications, (iii) fairness/supervision, (iv) involvement/identification and (v) matters relating to other jobs and companies which included some pay issues.

• **Strengths point**

The categories and number of responses allocated to each were as follow: workforce qualities (26items), historical strengths, like: client base, reputation, customer confident (16), organizational strengths, like: versatility persistence (13), Financial strengths (6), and technical strengths (2). The perceptions about management from the survey conducted regarding involvement, communication, respect, coaching, treatment and guidance employees obtain from their line managers: "I am often asked my opinion about job related issues (41%)", "I receive regular feedback on my work from my superiors(38%)", "I never know what's going on in other regions (84%)", "Omega does not treat its employees well (61%)", "The management of the company care about the conditions in which we work(22%)". It is evident that leadership styles, the regional managers and project leaders at omega have a very controlling style. Managers at omega are at solving problems, fairly treating employees, giving respect, exchanging and sharing of knowledge between employees and line managers.

• **Weakness point**

The most common responses (29 in total) fell into the management and investment coded group, like: poorly negotiated contracts, lack of investment in technology. The other categories that scored highly were:

Future planning (17), treatment of employees (14) and communication issues (12).were: Future planning (17), treatment of employees (14) and communication issues (12). The variations in employee discretion and managerial behavior, we can see the evidence on employee attitude affecting organizational commitment and employee satisfaction. Employee satisfaction with the sense of achievement they derive from their job varies. "My work gives me a sense of achievement (78%)", "I wish I had more time to produce better quality work (70%)", "I wish my job gave me more scope for learning new things (75%)", "My work is undervalued (60%)". it is show that Omega have very low scores for satisfaction in regard to career opportunities, training level due to the management's decision of rationalization. Employees who suffer from poor levels of satisfaction and motivation transfer their feelings to certain human resource practices such as absenteeism and high turnover rate.

- **The future action to take overcome the weaknesses**

In Omega, there is clearly no equilibrium between the contribution and gains and there is a negative relationship of attendance with the job-related factors. Omega should identification the associated to a certain extent with a number of work-related attitudes such as legitimacy, supervisor satisfaction, and motivation towards organizational goals, affective commitment, and their tendency to remain within the organization. It is necessary to have cooperation, long term employee effort, and coordination in a company. As per the survey, employees don't tend to stay in omega on a long-term basis due to their job dissatisfaction. "I anticipate still being with this company in five years' time (23%)", "if another company offered me a 15% increase in salary to join them, I would leave (75%)". In Omega, where working is a high knowledge based natured and majority of the employees are educated and well qualified, should drastic movement away from the traditional hierarchy design and max weber bureaucratic ideologies which in return places reliance on extensive communication for solving problem and coordination. This situation can be led to the importance of the immediate work group, hence work group or team identification is more salient for omega.

- **The approaches and advantage would provide**

In Omega, the employees are not given the opportunity to make decisions despite it having less bureaucracy, "I never know what's going on in other regions (84%)", "My immediate superior keeps me well informed about company issues (24%)", "Working for Omega gives me a strong sense of belonging to a group(23%)". So the personnel manager have used to the bottom-up approach should be adopted in the Omega, employees should be given the opportunity to make decisions, suggestions and should be able to share knowledge with their superiors. Herzberg developed a two factor motivation theory namely hygiene (extrinsic/job dissatisfaction) and motivators (intrinsic/job satisfiers) which can also be linked to McGregor's theory x and y. theory x relates to extrinsic because of the punishment involvement and theory y relates to intrinsic because employees will become satisfied when they perform work efficiently. The employees, we found a mixture of both, amongst the hygiene factors, company and administrative policies were not well laid out, supervision was too tight, salary was standardized, working conditions did not meet the employees needs, the interpersonal relations amongst team members were not good enough. However there was an increase in

intrinsic job satisfaction, the more dispersed the teams were from the employing organization. The greater salience of team identification for all employees, it may be that it is team identification rather than organizational that is a greater determinant of affective outcomes identification for software workers. All managers should motivate their employees using the intrinsic satisfiers like acknowledging their achievement, provide praise and recognition, ownership of their work, shown advantages of being an company's employee, warm welcoming and fair operating environment with communication policy and employees should be allowed to buy shares for a lower price. Possessing employees that are motivated results in having satisfied employees. Satisfaction is the key to decrease turnover rates and reduce absenteeism.

III. Conclusion and consequence

Develop an effective plan to improved job satisfaction it is necessary to identify existing employee attitudes to work. A commonly used method to establish the actions an organization needs to take is an attitude or opinion survey of the workforce. The purpose of the survey is to improve the quality of decision making based on better information. Have to solving the problems, fairly treating employees, giving respect, exchanging and sharing of knowledge between employees and line managers. And give them the opportunity to make decisions, the importance of job satisfaction lies not in its relationship with performance but with its stabilizing effects (reducing tardiness, absenteeism, and turnover) and through its effects on cohesion (increasing organizational citizenship behaviors and organizational commitment).

Based upon the results of the questionnaire comprised 83 items of which 68 were closed statements, 12 were open ended questions and three were of a demographic nature. The closed questions 67 sought to explore issues in five areas comprising: (i) general satisfaction, (ii) communications, (iii) fairness/supervision, (iv) involvement /identification and (v) matters relating to other jobs and companies which included some pay issues. Will lead to improved job satisfaction amongst the employee of the company. The questions sought further information from those respondents who believed that "I am willing to put myself out to help the company (81%)", "my job is worth doing (93%)", "I wish i had more time to produce better quality work (70%)", "I often learn new things in the course of my work (75%)", "I wish my job gave me more scope for learning new things (75%)", of the (i)General Satisfaction Issue. and "This company would benefit from having a greater number of formal policies(57%)". The manager needs to understand how best to make work more satisfying for staff and to overcome obstacles to effective performance. Must be given to the relationship between staff, and the nature and content of their jobs.

Action plan for the implementation: Organizational culture: refers to a system of shared meaning held by members that distinguishes the organization from other organizations. The Seven primary characteristics to capture the essence of an organization's culture: 1. Innovation and risk taking, 2. Attention to detail, 3. Outcome orientation, 4. People orientation, 5. Team orientation, 6. Aggressiveness, 7. Stability. Organizational culture a system of Shared meaning held by members that distinguishes the organization from other organizations. The potential benefits of improved job design are unlikely to be realized if attention is

focused on the content of jobs alone. Of equal, if not more, importance is the process by which redesign is carried out. This has led to recognition of the importance of management style and, increasingly of organization culture, Supervision involves technical knowledge, human relations skills and coordination of work activities. Effective supervision is necessary for job satisfaction and high levels of work performance. The contingency argument was seen to be moderated by culturally related influences in the areas of decision making, managerial roles, and behavioral expectations. Managers need to be aware of new psychological contracts and to adopt alternative styles of management. The work organization and the design of jobs can have a significant effect on staff and their levels of performance and productivity. Job satisfaction is important to the effectiveness and vitality of Companies, the importance of good managerial practices and how to make the best use of people. To motivation, promotion of good human relations is an integral part of the process of management and improved organizational performance.

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CHEK KEA: Master degree of Leader-Member Exchange and Unethical Pro-supervisor Behavior: Evidence from Cambodia.

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